

US-CHINA POWER STRUGGLE IN INDO-PACIFIC: A THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF MILITARY ALLIANCES AND STRATEGIC COUNTERMEASURES

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Abstract

Purpose This study explores the strategic competition between the United States and China in the Indo-Pacific region with a focus on military alliances, economic power and counter strategies as tools of influence. The Indo-pacific is framed not only as a geographic region but as a contested space of competing world orders—one aiming to preserve the status quo and the other seeking reshape it.

Methodology It employs a qualitative approach grounded in Neo-Realism and Power Transition Theory to examine the evolving dynamics of great-power rivalry between the US and China in the Indo-Pacific region. A theory-driven approach allows for the analysis of state actions whether as rational or irrational responses to systematic conditions—such as anarchy, power shifts and strategic uncertainty.

Findings The reviewed literature examines how the US and China navigate the shifting balance of power and security dynamics using Neo-Realism and Power Transition Theory as a guide. This paper doesn't merely catalogs military actions but analyzes alliance formation, deterrence mechanisms and strategic signaling. Drawing from contemporary developments and scholarly insights, the paper highlights the hedging strategies employed by the states that creates uncertain security environment.

INTRODUCTION

The Indo-pacific region has emerged as a flashpoint for competition between an emerging power and an existing power. An intensifying struggle for regional hegemony and dominance shapes the US and China strategic relations (Tausif & Ejaz, 2024). In order to achieve its objective of reshaping regional order, China has expanded its economic and military capabilities challenging the longstanding Security architecture established by US (Alenezi, 2024). Therefore, it is quite evident that the Indo-pacific region has become an arena of geo-political

contestation provoking strategic revamping on both sides.

Concerning China, it has been pursuing assertive policies such as the militarization of the South-China Sea and the implementation of Belt and Road initiative to set itself as the pre-eminent regional power and a challenger to US hegemony (Tausif & Ejaz, 2024). In response, the US has strengthened its military presence in the region and revitalized alliances demonstrating the intent to contain China in the Indo-pacific region (Keen et al., 2024). Mehta (2019) asserts that the Washington has pursued the

objective of "free and open Indo-pacific" as reflected through the former's expansion and solidification of partnerships with Japan, Australia, India and ASEAN states.

Notably, the strengthening of military alliances has been the focal point of US counter strategies towards China. Such kind of cooperative security approach is exemplified by the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (QUAD), comprising the US, Japan, Australia, and India which is aimed at countering Chinese influence through joint military exercises, intelligence sharing, and coordinated regional engagement (Grieco & Kavanagh, 2024). Furthermore, a trilateral agreement between the US, UK and Australia namely the AUKUS pact, narrates US commitment for advanced military technologies including nuclear powered submarines and to enhance its deterrence capabilities in the Indo-Pacific theater by forging deeper ties (Novita, 2022). On the other hand, China is pursuing asymmetric strategies including gray-zone tactics, maritime militia operations, and economic coercion in order to undermine the US influence while avoiding full-scale confrontation (Cuong et al., 2024). China has fostered partnerships with regional actors like Pakistan and Russia and recalibrating People's Liberation Army's Navy on modern lines. This argument is reinforced by Robert E. Hamilton's 2025 report of the foreign Policy Research Institute that Chinese and Russian Naval joint exercises has been considerably increased in 2024 highlighting "Ocean 2024" alone involving 90,000 troops and total of 500 ships. Such activities depict china's committment towards the military cooperation and tactical partnerships in the Indo-Pacific region.

This tug of war between two great powers signifies a broader contest over existing international order and future of balance of power in the Indo-pacific region that is not merely about territorial disputes or maritime control (He & Liu, 2024). Analytically speaking, the risk of miscalculation and unintended escalation grows as both states deepen their strategic footprints in such a crucial region.

Literature Review

Undoubtedly, one of the most highlighted geopolitical rivalries of the 21st century is the US-China power struggle in the Indo-Pacific region. It seems that both the nations are trying to establish

their dominance in the region economically as well as militarily. The US has strengthened its hold to contain China's increasing influence in the Indo-Pacific region by forming security alliances such as AUKUS and the Quad and through Bilateral defense treaties with South Korea, Japan, and the Philippines (Goldstein, 2020). This great power has been a staunch supporter of freedom of navigation in the South China Sea and Taiwan Strait, blue territories claimed by China. As a countermeasure, China is reforming its army on modern grounds and expanding its naval power by entering into strategic partnerships with Russia and Pakistan (Yesi Riana, 2021). This study will examine how the US-China military alliances and counter strategies impacts the global politics and regional peace. Additionally, the role of international actors such as India and Australia in the US-China power struggle will be analyzed as depicted in the form of military partnerships such as AUKUS and QUAD.

Historical context of the US-China power struggle in the Indo-Pacific:

The game of dominance between such two great competitors gained prominence after WWII when America signed bilateral defense treaties with Japan (1951), South Korea (1953), and the Philippines (1951) to contain the spread of communism in the region. In addition to these security alliances, US Pacific Command, which maintained a network of naval bases, i.e., Guam, Okinawa, facilitated US military presence in Asia and reinforced the role of the US as a security guarantor (Roy, 2022). With the introduction of economic reforms in 1978, China experienced rapid modernization (Shi, 2022). At the beginning of the 21st century, China claimed rights over the South China Sea and pursued Area Denial (A2) policies. The US responded with the establishment of AUKUS (2021) and the revival of the QUAD (2017) under the Obama administration to challenge China's rise (Priyanto Suharto, 2024). Meanwhile, China deepened its ties with Pakistan, Russia, and ASEAN states. This power struggle reflects the shift of power where China presents a challenge to US dominance and the US struggles to maintain its hegemony. Taking into account the concerns that use of force would be perilous and costly to such an extent that nuclear war could be

imminent, PRC has pursued a different approach "grey zone" tactics emphasizing on psychological pressure and military projection on Taiwan while avoiding to surpass the limit of lethal violence (Saunders & McGuinness, 2021).

US Military Alliances in the Indo-Pacific:

The QUAD (Quadrilateral Security Dialogue) including Japan, India, Australia and the United States was established in 2007 with activities primarily focused on military cooperation and security strategies as well as regional diplomacy and governance. In 2020, the QUAD stated that China must not attempt to militarize the region and that there should be freedom of navigation and flight over the South China Sea (Keerthiraj & Sekiyama, 2023). In 2021 Malabar exercise held on the coast of Guam involved the naval forces of the partner states engaging in maritime security, and anti-submarine warfare (Karambelkar, 2021). In 2021, it was reaffirmed by them that China must adhere to the United Nations Convention on the LAWS OF THE SEA. However, it was about March 13, 2023 when the members of AUKUS adopted an incremental approach and decided to develop an SSN-AUKUS submarine which will be designed according to next-generation nuclear powered submarine of UK while integrating the innovative technology of US and Australia. This was aimed at establishing submarines with nuclear capabilities and enhanced hypersonic weapons and undersea capabilities (Childs, N., 2023). Besides these treaties, according to AP news (2024), Japan hosts nearly 50,000 and South Korea approximately 28500 US troops. The EDCA pact with the Philippines allows rotational access to Philippines bases to the US military. According to Lema K. (2023), the EDCA sites have been increased from 5 to 9 highlighting its strategic expansion.

China's Counter Strategies:

Reciprocally, China is investing in Belt and Road Initiative which integrates economic and military dimensions highlighting China's response through strategic investments. BRI is seen not only as a development but also a deliberate geo-political counter strategy. A crucial meeting was held in July, 2022 initiated by Chinese Foreign Minister Wang Yi with 10 Pacific Island countries as a part of China's

diplomatic efforts to enhance its economic and security partnerships under BRI (Pratama et al., 2023). Furthermore, China aims to develop port facilities in key locations such as Gawadar, Hambantota, and Djibouti which will reshape the global political dimensions. China has also increased joint military exercises, arms trade, and diplomatic efforts through SCO and CPEC. On modern lines, The People's Liberation Army has reformed itself and is heavily investing in AI-driven warfare and strengthening its footing in the South China Sea and Taiwan Strait (Maher, 2023).

Geopolitical and Strategic Implications

The Taiwan Strait is the tripping point where China vows reunification of Taiwan even if it has to use force and has pledged to support Taiwan in case China initiates a forceful reunification. This conflict could escalate into a full-scale US-China war where regional allies Australia, Japan, Pakistan, and Russia would become involved (Maher, 2023). Similarly, North Korea's programs to enhance its nuclear capability backed by China serve as a threat to US security. Further escalation could destabilize the whole region and ASEAN's neutral stance on these and South China disputes is adding to the increased tensions. The regional allies are pursuing their interests where some ASEAN countries benefitting from China's economic policies choose to remain silent, and others seek US help to build their economies (Narain & Strat, 2025). Apparently, the ability of the United Nations to mediate in these security issues is limited because China and Russia oppose US-led initiatives.

Theoretical framework

Neo-realism developed by Kenneth Waltz contends that the international system is anarchic and compels states to rely on self-help mechanisms to ensure their survival (Ogunbanjo, 2021). Insightfully, some of the key concepts linked to this major theory of International Relations are Security dilemma, Relative gains, and polarity. When one state increases its power to secure itself, it is perceived as a threat by other states and they get trapped in an arms race (Vander Vennet & Geeraerts, 2023). From a neo-realist perspective, the international system lacks a central authority and survival is the top priority for states. After the Cold War ended, the post 1991,

world became unipolar with the US as the hegemon (Liu & He, 2025). China's assertive territorial claims and maritime expansion are best interpreted through offensive realism, where rising powers seek to revise the status quo to secure their dominance (Ye, 2024). The revitalization of the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (QUAD) reflects the US's balancing response rooted in defensive realism, which aims to preserve regional order without confrontation (Zeeshan et al., 2025).

On the basis of preceding analysis, Neo-realism argues that states are more worried about relative gains which also explains why the US and its allies are more skeptical about China's trade policies. Security dilemma explains how China's increasing economic influence in the region serves as a threat to the US and the formation of military alliances such as AUKUS and QUAD by the US to counterbalance China (Alenezi, 2024). Similarly the power struggle between the US and China seems quite relevant to "Thucydides trap" given by the Greek historian Thucydides who explains it as a dilemma created when an emerging power challenges the existing dominant hegemon. So, accordingly, rising power China is challenging the supremacy of the US who aims to preserve its status quo (Khan et al., 2024).

Profoundly, the Power transition theory developed by A.F.K Organski focuses on hierarchy rather than anarchy and introduces the concept of a hegemon state with less powerful states below it (Mukhtar, 2024). PTT suggests that international conflict is most likely to occur when a rising power approaches or surpasses the power of the dominant state in the international system. Peace is maintained as long as the hegemon is stronger than all the challengers (Debnath, 2024). When a rising power nears parity with a dominant state and is dissatisfied with the global order, it leads to conflict-led decoupling and coalition-building efforts to forestall China's ascension also complies with PTT (Hu, 2022).

China, being partially dissatisfied with the current US-led international order, seeks to reshape global institutions and regional dynamics, especially in the Indo-Pacific. After WW II, the United States, has functioned as the system's hegemon, shaping global norms through institutions like the United Nations, World Bank, and the World Trade Organization. It has largely benefitted from a liberal international

order which is based on open trade, security alliances, and democratic values (Steff, 2024). Although China has participated in many international institutions, it often criticizes their western-centric nature, revealing a degree of dissatisfaction with the current global order—a key trigger in PTT. Projects such the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB), and expansive territorial claims in the South China Sea signal Beijing's aspiration to reshape regional and global order (Liu & He, 2025). Through the lens of PTT, once can see that as China closes the power gap (measured in GDP, military strength, technological innovation, and diplomatic influence), the systemic pressure on the United States to resist China's rise increases. This resistance is visible in US strategies like the Pivot to Asia, the creation of AUKUS, the strengthening of QUAD, and economic decoupling efforts in critical sectors like semiconductors and AI. To conclude, PTT explains that China's rise challenges US dominance, and both states are preparing for potential confrontation, even if they publicly advocate stability.

The focus of the existing literature has been on traditional security measures such as increasing military buildup, deploying military units in sensitive areas, and traditional military alliances. This literature so far has either evaluated US-China rivalry through the lens of Neo-realism or Power transition theory but the combined application of both lenses remains unexplored. There is a paucity of research examining whether China's evolving strategy is accommodationist or revisionist (Ye, 2024). Neo-realism and power transition theory offer valuable insights into great power dynamics but a comprehensive analysis that integrates both theories to assess the efficacy of regional alliances and strategies is to be explored yet.

Research Questions

- How do neo-realist and power transition theories explain the evolving strategic rivalry between the United States and China in the Indo-Pacific region?
- Does the transformation of regional coalitions such as the QUAD reflect the tenets of offensive realism or power transition theory?

Methodology

This research employs a qualitative approach based on theoretical context such as neo-realism and power transition theory to uncover the shifting trends of the complex geopolitical realities. This approach highlights the importance of analyzing the state actions to understand the great power politics in contemporary world. The dynamic aspects of this research are analytical and explanatory and also applies comparative case analysis contrasting the US response to China's maritime assertiveness with China's evolving diplomatic and economic strategies, to assess whether they reflect patterns of balancing, accommodation, or revisionism. Secondary sources, including peer-reviewed journal articles, institutional analyses and reputable books are critically reviewed to contextualize the strategic behavior of both powers. This methodology enables a rigorous assessment of the manifestation of macro-level theories of international relations in regional behavior, with implications for global order, alliance politics, and future conflict scenarios.

Analysis

The deeper understanding of US-China rivalry can be better grasped through the lens of neo-realism particularly Kenneth Waltz concept of structural realism which emphasizes the anarchic nature of international system and pursuit of power as the primary driver of state behavior (Cuong et al., 2024). In such a system where there's no central authority, states maximize their security and engage in balancing behaviors. Critically, the emergence of China as a leading power in the region can be interpreted to be a natural response to the unipolarity established by the US after the cold war (Alenezi, 2024).

Washington's external balancing strategies to deter Chinese assertiveness through reinforcing alliances like the Quad and AUKUS, and engaging in forward military deployments are also covered by neo-realist tendencies (Tausif and Ejaz 2024). Unlike classical realism, that holds human nature or leadership intentions responsible for states being hungry for power or dominance neo-realism attributes this to system constraints. To respond to China's increasing influence in the region reflected through A2/AD systems and maritime expansionism, US has nurtured force posture realignments, strategic access

agreements, and defense cooperation with littoral states such as the Philippines and Japan (Aurangzeb et al., 2025).

Power transition theory further sharpens this analysis. Propounded by A.F.K Organski, PTT asserts that a dominant power (The US) will face increasing challenges and resistance when a rising contender (China) approaches parity and is dissatisfied with the existing international order (Wallis et al., 2024). This framework is well applicable in the US-China rivalry as many scholars predict a disorder in global power structure as China continues its rising supremacy in economic dominance and military diligence. China's behavior reflects dissatisfaction as it questions US freedom of navigation, rejects international arbitration in the South China Sea and creation of alternative institutions like the Asian infrastructure investment bank. Hence, Indo-Pacific has become a bone of contention where the transition of power provokes friction and conflict.

The theoretical implications of PTT are manifested in the intensification of military signaling and hedging behaviors across the Indo-Pacific. China's military buildup, particularly maritime capabilities is not merely aimed to secure trade routes but to assert regional leadership (Kucukdegirmenci, 2024). This theory remains quite significant in evaluating Sino-US power struggle as Organski argued that China's strategic rise to the global arena by means of domestic development would be "spectacular", China's strength is expected to increase substantially and will prove to be an ultimate threat to the western hegemony (Ormeci et al., 2024). Power Transition theory explains that when a new actor rises to power and challenges the hegemony of existing powers, it can lead to a global conflict. The declining hegemon, the US, struggles to maintain its dominance through shifts in trade policies such as trade sanctions, tariffs, economic decoupling, and military partnerships while China continues to be a challenge for it through projects such as BRI.

The people's liberation army navy's enhancement both in quality and sophistication supports a grand strategy aimed at regional preeminence (Popescu, 2024). This way the rise of China poses a threat to the hegemony of the United States so the US tries to maintain its primacy. Moreover, China's naval buildup, expansion in the South China Sea, and Belt

and Road Initiative are interpreted by the US as attempts to alter the regional balance of power (R. Liu, 2025). Concurrently, the US has expanded its military presence to wider geographic area, reactivated base related pacts and conducted joint exercises to signal preparedness and unity (Foster & Clark, 2024). According to neo-realist perspective, such balancing practices also lead to Security dilemma where one's states defensive actions are perceived to be offensive by another state which promotes arms race and escalates mistrust (Kumar, 2023). Both have acquired satellite-based surveillance systems, hypersonic missile technologies and had been expanding cyber warfare units for years. There's a risk of miscalculations particularly in hotspots like the Taiwan Strait and the South China Sea because the line between deterrence and provocation has been blurred (Xiying, 2019). From realistic point of view, there's an assumption that states in actual aspire to have maximum power and security in the structural anarchic competition. This perspective is truly exemplified by the great power competition between the United States and China with both rival challenging their counter parts. Moreover, the anarchic international system has constrained the Indo-Pacific middle powers, so they engage in soft balancing which is economic alignment with China and maintenance of defense ties with US (Lee, 2024). For instance, India has participated in QUAD while maintained trade with China. Similarly, this nuanced strategic behavior is exemplified in Vietnam's naval cooperation with the US despite its proximity to Beijing (Cuong et al., 2024). This aligns with Waltz's assertion that structure, not ideology, determines state actions.

It would be prudent enough to contend that alliances are not just military tools but mechanisms of strategic signaling in a broader power transition narrative. Considering this, AUKUS reflects both a technological edge and a commitment to uphold maritime norms while China has leverage as it can use belt and Road initiative for dual use military logistics.

Conclusion

The strategic rivalry between the United States and China is emblematic of shifting trends in the global power structure. Neo-realism and power transition theory explains the ongoing tussle for dominance in an anarchic international order as to how states

ensure survival and power. The Indo-Pacific thus becomes a complex, multipolar space where one can observe the intersection of hard power diplomacy, technology, and economic statecraft. The findings suggest that miscalculations based on threat perception and security dilemmas might escalate the existing complexity of the conflict.

REFERENCES:

- Goldstein, A. US-China Rivalry in the twenty-first century: Déjà vu and Cold War II. *China Int Strategy Rev.* 2, 48-62 (2020).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s42533-020-00036-W>
- Sari, Y. R. Y., & Oktavian, R. (2024) AUKUS: The Rise of Chinese Might and the US Response *Global Strategis*, 18(1), 227-244.
<https://doi.org/10.20473/jgs.18.1.2024.227-244>
- Li, Mingjiang. (2020). The Belt and Road Initiative: geo-economics and Indo-Pacific security competition. *International Affairs*. 96. 169-187,
<http://te.doi.org/10.1093/ia/liz240>
4. Alenezi, D.A (2024), "US rebalance strategy to Asia and US-China rivalry in South China Sea from the perspective of the offensive realism", *Review of Economics and Political Science*, Vol. 9 No. 2, pp. 102-115.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/REPS-10-2019-013>
5. Suharto, Priyanto & Timur, Fauzia & Sutanto, Rudi. (2024). The development of AUKUS in the Indo-Pacific region and its influence on Indonesia's policy as a global maritime fulcrum. *Journal of Infrastructure, Policy and Development*. 8. 4076.
<http://Adx.doi.org/10.24294/jipd.v17.4076>.
6. Amin, Huma & Rafique, Arslan. (2021). 18-23 The Maritime Rise of China in Indo-Pacific and Indo-US Counter Balancing Approach. *Journal of Political Science and International Relations*. 4. 18-23.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.11648/j.jpsir.20210401.13>

7. Shi, X. Beyond AUKUS: the emerging grand maritime alliance. *China Int Strategy Rev*, 4, 248-267 (2022).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/542533-022-00123-0>
8. Keerthiraj, Sekiyama T. The Rise of China and Evolving Defense Cooperation between India and Japan. *Social Sciences*. 2023, 12(6):333.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/socsc.12060333>
9. Mather, N. (2023), "US-China policy amid a persistent strategy, is conflict over Taiwan inevitable?", *Review of Economics and Political Science*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/REPS-05-2023-0040>
10. Saunders, P. C., & McGuiness, J. (2021, May 26). The changing balance of military power in the Indo-Pacific region. Hoover Institution.
<https://www.hoover.org/research/changing-balance-military-power-indo-pacific>: region
11. Childs, N. (2023). The AUKUS Anvil: Promise and Peril. *Survival: Global Politics and Strategy*, 65(5), 7-24. Taylor & Francis.
<https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edited-by/10.4324/9781003429388-1/aukus-anvil-promise-peril> nick-childs
12. AP News. (2024, August 29). Japan is home to more than 50,000 U.S. troops as alliance deepens amid China concerns, <https://apnews.com/article/japan-us-military-command-missile-china-4e9714cb01cfef7b6db8fb1a5df771e4>
13. AP News. (2024, October 4). The US and South Korea reach new deal on costs for the American troop presence. <https://apnews.com/article/us-south-korea-military-presence-costs-4951973206a7068038bc3616f2e41690>
14. Lema, K. (2023, April 3). Philippines reveals locations of 4 new strategic sites for U.S. military pact. Reuters.
<https://www.reuters.com/world/asia-pacific/philippines-reveals-locations-4-new-strategic-sites-us-military-pact-2023-04-03>
15. Ormeci, O., Kisacik, S., & Helvacikoylu, G. (2024). U.S.-China competition: A power transition perspective. *China Quarterly of International Strategic Studies*.
<https://doi.org/10.1142/s2377740024500015>
16. Steff, R. (2024). The US-China Great Power Competition in the Indo-Pacific: Colliding Strategies and Ambitions. In: *New Zealand's Geopolitics and the US-China Competition. Global Political Transitions*. Palgrave Macmillan, Singapore.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-96-0282-7_5
17. Liu, F., & He, K. (2025). China's bilateral relations, order transition, and the Indo-Pacific dynamics. In *WORLD SCIENTIFIC (EUROPE) eBooks* (pp. 1–32).
<https://doi.org/10.1142/97818006163180002>
18. Htwe, T. M. (2024). China's strategic influence and rivalries in Southeast Asia. In *Advances in finance, accounting, and economics book series*(pp. 119–146).
<https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-7393-4.ch004>
19. Debnath, B. (2024). From Assertion to Accommodation?: Explaining China's Evolving response to the Indo-Pacific Strategy. *Journal of Polity and Society*, 16(1). Retrieved from <https://journalspoliticalscience.com/index.php/i/article/view/269>
20. Zhenshuo Hu. (2022). The Indo-Pacific Strategy from the Perspective of Offensive Realism. *Journal of research in social science and humanities*, 1(1), 36–41. retrieved from <https://www.pioneerpublisher.com/jrssh/article/view/39>
21. Farnillah, A. N., & Paksi, A. (2023). The China-US trade dispute in Neo-Realism perspective and settlement of dispute by the WTO. *Jurnal Inovasi Ilmu Sosial Dan Politik (JISoP)*, 5(2), 130–140. <https://doi.org/10.33474/jisop.v5i2.20089>

22. Muhammad Zeeshan, Muhammad Javed, Atif Anwer Dar, & Dr. Adnan Nawaz*. (2025). Strategic Competition between China and the U.S. in Southeast Asia: ASEAN's Essential Role. *Journal of Social Signs Review*, 3(1), 453-468. Retrieved from <https://socialsignsreview.com/index.php/12/article/view/92>
- 23.. Ye, M. (2024). Security in context (SiC): a novel theoretical and empirical approach to the US-China rivalry. *Review of Social Economy*, 1-27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00346764.2024.2312414>
24. Liu, R.-F. (2023). Reinforcing Wedging: Assessing China's Southeast Asia Policy in the Context of Indo-Pacific Strategy. 23, 277-306.
25. Grieco, K. A., & Kavanagh, J. (2024). The elusive Indo-Pacific Coalition: Why Geography Matters. *The Washington Quarterly*, 47(1), 103-121. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0163660x.2024.2326324>
26. Cuong, N. M., Chelabi, K., Anjum, S., Sateeshchandra, N. G., Samoylenko, S., Silwizya, K., & Nghiem, T. (2024). US-China global competition and dilemma for Vietnam's strategic choices in the South China Sea conflict. *Heritage and Sustainable Development* ISSN 2712-0554, 6(1), 349-364. <https://doi.org/10.37868/hsd.v6i1.550>
27. Tausif, S. ., & Khushboo Ejaz. (2024). US-China Strategic Rivalry in Asia Pacific: Opportunities and Challenges for Regional States. *Journal of Nautical Eye and Strategic Studies*, 4(1), 53-72. <https://doi.org/10.58932/MULG0033>
28. He, K., & Liu, F. (2024). China's bilateral relations, order transition, and the Indo Pacific dynamics. In *WORLD SCIENTIFIC (EUROPE)* eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.1142/q0480>
29. Muneeb Aurangzeb , Dr. Syed Shuja Uddin, Arjumand Farooq, & Rao Aqib Ali. (2025). Offensive Realism and the Pacific Ocean: Understanding Geopolitical Rivalries through Mearsheimer's Lens. *Policy Journal of Social Science Review*, 3(1), 268-278. Retrieved from <https://journalofsocialsciencereview.com/index.php/PJSSR/article/view/108>
30. Wallis, J., McNeill, H., Rose, M., & Tidwell, A. (2024). Power and influence in the Pacific Islands. In *Routledge eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003496441>
31. Mehta, S. (2019), The Free and Open Indo-Pacific strategy: A way forward, *Policy Forum*, July 25. Available at: <https://www.policyforum.net/the-free-and-open-indo-pacific-strategy-a-way-forward/> (accessed: 05.04.2023).
31. Kumar, S. (2023). Shifting balance of power and the formation of AUKUS in the Indo-Pacific region. *Australian Journal of Maritime & Ocean Affairs*, 16(4), 456-476. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18366503.2023.2271254>
32. Lee, S. (2024). U.S.-China Technology Competition and the Emergence of Techno-Economic Statecraft in East Asia: High Technology and Economic-Security Nexus. *Journal of Chinese Political Science*, 29(3), 397-416. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11366-023-09878-8>
32. Novita, A. A. D. (2022). AUKUS Alliance: United States Strategic interest in Indo-Pacific. *Journal Diplomasi Pertahanan*, 8(1) <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/55b4/7790ad616c33928dfb0cdf9fb61e9c964a13.pdf3>.
33. Hamilton, R. E. (2025, January 28). Setting the stage: An overview of Chinese and Russian interests and influence in the Indo-Pacific. *Foreign Policy Research Institute*. <https://www.fpri.org/article/2025/01/setting-the-stage-an-overview-of-chinese-and-russian-interests-and-influence-in-the-indo-pacific/>

34. Roy, D. (2022). America's deep Rationale for INDOPACOM. In Evidence-Based Approaches to Peace and Conflict Studies (pp. 19-32). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-5268-5_2
35. Karambelkar, A. (2021, September 4). The QUAD Navies Exercise for the Second Time. Vivekananda International Foundation. <https://www.vifindia.org/article/2021/september/04/the-quad-navies-exercise-for-the-second-time>
36. Narain, Saurav & Strat, Francesa. (2025). Strategic Alliances and Contested Seas: a Deep dive into China-ASEAN Relations. National security and the future.
37. Ogunbanjo, M. A. (2021, July 25). Neo-Realism and Neo-Liberalism in global Politics: Towards assessing the intellectual siblings. <https://ijhumas.com/ojs/index.php/niujs/article/view/1222>
38. Vander Vennet, N., & Geeraerts, G. (2023). Uncertainty, system structure, and the security dilemma: Exploring the structure-uncertainty nexus. Manuscript submitted for publication. Retrieved from <https://researchportal.vub.be/en/publications/uncertainty-system-structure-and-the-security-dilemma-exploring-t>
39. Mukhtar, G. (2024). Power transition in global international order: A study of Chinese rise. Review Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities, <https://rjosh.org/index.php/rjosh/article/view/6>
40. Kucukdegirmenci, O. (2024). China's Rise, China's Regional Initiatives, and Japan's Perception of China. In: The Shifting Sands of Japan's Security Landscape. Palgrave Macmillan, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-7578-1_6
41. Popescu, A. I. C. (2024). The 'China's dream' - the grand strategy of transforming China into a global Maritime power. Cogent Social Sciences, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2024.2414873>
42. Foster, J. B., & Clark, B. (2024). Imperialism in the Indo-Pacific—An Introduction. Monthly Review, 1-23. https://doi.org/10.14452/mr-076-03-2024-07_1
43. Xiyang, Z. (2019). Unbalanced deterrence: coercive threat, reassurance and the US-China rivalry in Taiwan strait. The Pacific Review, 34(4), 547-576. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09512748.2019.1697353>
44. Keen, M., & Tidwell, A. (2024). Geopolitics in the Pacific Islands: Playing for advantage. Lowy Institute. <https://www.lowyinstitute.org/sites/default/files/2024-01/KEEN%20TIDWELL%20PDF%20v8.pdf>

